

CHARACTER EDUCATION MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF GRADUATES AT DARUL HIKAM JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL BANDUNG

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to get an overview or information about how character education management is implemented based on (planning, organizing, implementing and supervising) in schools and its influence on the quality of graduates. This research was conducted at Darul Hikam Junior High School, Bandung. This research uses management theory from G.R. Terry as a theoretical basis for looking at the implementation of character education management at Darul Hikam Junior High School, Bandung City. This research uses a qualitative approach with analytical descriptive methods where the researcher aims to get an in-depth picture of the research problem using observation, interviews and study of school documents. The results of the research show that character education management in educational units must start by equalizing the perceptions of the school community and must be expressed in the school's vision and mission. Furthermore, character education must be carried out in the form of positive habits that form a culture of character as desired by the school. Character education must be internalized in intracurricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities and must use valid assessment instruments to assess the implementation of character education and its sustainability in the educational unit.

Keywords: Management, Education, Character, Quality of Graduat.

INTRODUCTION

Basic education in elementary schools (SD) and junior high schools (SMP) provides a foundation for competency development for students in the age range of 6 -15 years. Basic education not only provides a foundation that is related to cognition, but also provides a basis for character in children which will later become the child's character when they grow up.

Character refers to the traits, values, attitudes, and principles that shape a person's personality. Character is an aspect that reflects how a person behaves, interacts with other people, and responds to situations or challenges in life. Character includes various elements including integrity, honesty, discipline, empathy, caring, responsibility, courage, humility, tolerance, cooperation, respect.

Character development in basic education is important because it helps students become good, responsible individuals and have a strong moral foundation. Good character helps students in their social relationships, education, and careers throughout life.

Character development carried out in basic education units ideally instills a strong character foundation in elementary school students, however, the Ministry of PPPA reported that in 2018, it was found that 62 percent of girls and boys experienced one or more forms of violence throughout their lives. A survey conducted by the Ministry of PPPA also found that one in 11

girls and one in 17 boys experienced sexual violence. Character education has become an increasingly important issue at various levels of education, including Junior High School (SMP). Character education aims to form individuals who are not only academically intelligent, but also have strong moral, ethical values and positive attitudes. Middle school is a very important educational stage in forming students' character because they are in a very critical period of development. Therefore, it is important to explore and analyze the implementation of character learning management in junior high schools.

Darul Hikam Junior High School is one of the oldest private schools in the city of Bandung because it was founded in 1982, and has the motto "Being Achievement". From this motto, it can be seen that Darul Hikam Junior High School has the desire to strengthen character education before achievement. If you look at the motto of this school which prioritizes character education, graduates or students from this school must be students who are cognitively, affectively/attitudes and have good competence. These are the things that make researchers want to examine what the quality of graduates from Darul Hikam Junior High School is like as a result of implementing character education management at Darul Hikam Junior High School.

The quality of a school's graduates is the quality or standard of education produced by a school in terms of academic achievement, student abilities, and their preparation for life after school. The quality of graduates is influenced by various factors, including curriculum, teaching methods, facilities and student support. The higher the quality of a school's graduates, the better the preparation given to students to face future challenges, whether in college, the world of work, or personal life.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is analytical descriptive with a natural qualitative approach. The choice of this approach is based on the consideration that what will be sought in this research is something that provides a picture that depicts complex social reality, such as behavior, motivation, actions and utterances, both oral and written, as a whole in a specific problem context that is not made up. Create by utilizing various scientific methods.

According to Sugiyono (2018) qualitative research methods are research methods used to research the conditions of natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation (combination), data analysis is inductive, and qualitative research results emphasize the meaning of on generalization. This research can be classified as field research or descriptive field research, namely analyzing and presenting facts systematically about the actual state of the object. In this case the author takes the object of field research at Darul Hikam Junior High School Bandung, where the researcher will describe the results of research at Darul Hikam Junior High School Bandung regarding the research problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Well-implemented character education management where there is a process of planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring has been proven to have an impact on increasing the quality of a school's graduates. This can be seen in the character education carried out by Darul Hikam Junior High School Bandung. Based on the findings and interpretation, it shows that the character education management implemented at Darul Hikam Junior High School has a steady system which includes management functions (planning, organizing, actuating and controlling) and this steady system has an impact on increasing the quality of Darul Hikam Junior High School graduates.

1) Planing

Baharudin in Sulhan (2015) said that planning is a decision-making activity regarding what targets (objectives) will be achieved, what actions will be taken in order to achieve the goals or objectives and who will carry out the tasks.

It was further stated in Sulhan (2015) that planning sources include: (1) top leadership/school/madrasah policies, (2) results of supervision, (3) future needs, (4) discovery of new problems, (5) Initiatives within institutions/institutions, (6) Initiatives from outside.

This is in accordance with what is done by Darul Hikam Junior High School where there is a policy from the Foundation regarding the development of morals and achievement, then the results of evaluating school achievements and parent satisfaction surveys the previous year, adolescent development problems related to the character and goals of the school as a school. Islam is the basis for character education management planning at this school.

Character education planning originating from Foundation policies and school achievements as well as parent satisfaction surveys, as well as recent problems are used as the basis for making educational policies, in this case in preparing the vision and mission and school programs. The Darul Hikam Foundation has 7 Values of Taqwa Character Building as basic values or "Core Values". These 7 TCB values are internalized in character education and are expected to become culture. This culture was narrowed down to 10 Cultures of Moral Achievement.

This planning must be carried out at the beginning of the school year by involving all school stakeholders and planned or prepared in the form of a workshop. As a result of this workshop, the school has program priorities that will be planned and implemented in the next school year.

In relation to character education which will have an impact on the quality of graduates, it is necessary to internalize core values into all aspects of school education. The aspects referred to here are apart from intra-curricular, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, but also forms of activities that lead to the formation of the desired student profile, especially regarding their character in the form of positive habits, involving students in various kinds of activities to provide positive experiences. And positive activities that can develop student character.

At Darul Hikam Junior High School, character education is strengthened by a learning culture that is practiced from class VII to class IX. The character values taught must be entrenched and ingrained in every member of Darul Hikam Junior High School. This culture is called the Culture of Moral Achievement. 10 Moral Cultures for Achievement at Darul Hikam Junior High School:

1. Worship diligently and get used to praying in congregation
2. Be disciplined and study/work hard
3. Clean, green and smoke-free environment
4. Islamic relationships, especially between men and women
5. Be polite in speaking and acting
6. Be compact and care about fellow friends
7. Honest and responsible for tasks
8. Independent and pioneer in Virtue
9. Amar Ma'ruf Nahyi Munkar tradition
10. Tradition of achieving achievements and becoming champions

2) Organizing,

With regard to organizing, Salhan (2015) says that organizing is the process of determining, grouping and arranging the various activities needed to achieve goals, placing people in these activities, providing physical factors that are suitable for the environment (work requirements). And the appointment of a delegated authority relationship to each person related to the implementation of each expected activity. The organization of character education at Darul Hikam Junior High School is seen as a follow-up to the planning that was made at the beginning of the year by the school. The organization of the curriculum (intracurricular, extracurricular and co-curricular) as an educational tool for students has been adjusted to the needs of students and the priorities of school programs that have been set as goals. Organizing student activities as an enhancement system for all curriculum programs in the form of habituation, student activities are directed towards the formation of student profiles with character and of course support the learning culture that is developed. This results in student achievement as the fruit of character education that is developed

3) Actuating

According to Koontz and O'Donnell in Salhan (2015), implementation is a close relationship between individual aspects resulting from the regulation of subordinates so that they can be understood and the effective and efficient division of work to achieve real organizational goals. The implementation of character education management can be seen at Darul Hikam Junior High School, where the principal is the central figure who manages the running of the education. The school principal forms a leadership team to be able to share authority where

each person assigned has the authority to carry out character education. For the curriculum, a deputy principal is appointed with two staff, and for the deputy principal for student affairs, a deputy is appointed with the assistance of two staff. The principal also appoints the person responsible for each school activity and is directly under the coordination of the deputy principal. Each person in charge provides a report to the deputy principal. The school principal controls program implementation through weekly coordination for evaluation and follow-up on program improvements.

4) Controlling

The final phase of management is controlling. Controlling in the first sense is supervision. Supervision in character education management according to Sulhan (2015) is the key to success in overall education management, it needs to be seen comprehensively, integrated, and not limited to certain things. This supervision can also be in the form of an assessment where the results of this assessment are used as data to improve the program in the future.

Supervision of character education at Darul Hikam Junior High School can be seen when the principal becomes the Steering Committee for each activity, although for each activity there is a person in charge, each person in charge must be responsible to the school principal. The principal in this case carries out a supervisory function. The controlling function in management is to ensure that planned goals can be achieved. Therefore, evaluation is needed in this controlling phase in addition to supervision. Character education at Darul Hikam Junior High School is carried out to achieve the school's goals as stated in the school's vision, assessed with a comprehensive assessment.

a. Attitude Assessment

Attitude assessment is an activity carried out by educators to obtain descriptive information about student behavior. Data is taken from the achievement of the habit of worship and the achievement of students' social values in the Social Workbook. As a reinforcement for the teacher, friend or guidance counselor/psychologist's assessment of the student.

b. Cognitive and Competence Assessment

Knowledge or Cognitive assessment is an activity carried out to measure students' mastery of knowledge. Meanwhile, Competencies or skills assessment is an activity carried out to measure students' ability to apply knowledge in carrying out certain tasks. In practice, these two assessments are integrated and made into one value. Knowledge assessment is carried out through written tests, oral tests, and assignments according to the competencies being assessed. Knowledge assessment is carried out through stages:

1. Prepare An Assessment Plan;
2. Develop Assessment Instruments;
3. Carry Out Assessments;
4. Utilize The assessment results; And
5. Report the assessment results in the form of numbers on a scale of 0-100 and a description.

Knowledge Assessment consists of: Process Values/Daily Assessments (PH), Mid-Semester Summative Assessments (ASTS), End-of-Semester Summative Assessments (ASAS)/End-of-Year Summative Assessments (ASAT) and End-of-Level Summative Assessments (ASAJ).

1. Several provisions relating to class promotion.

Students are declared to be promoted to class if they have reached the minimum completeness criteria (KKM) in all subjects,

2. Complete all subjects.

3. Obtain a minimum good score in the final assessment for all subjects in the religious and noble morals group, the citizenship and personality group in the aesthetics subjects' group, and the physical, sports and health subjects' group.

4. Complete memorization of the Al Quran at least 1 juz for each level and minimum Tahsin level at Basic Level 2 level 7th grade to be able to go up to class 8, Advanced for class 8 so you can go up to class 9

5. Complete the PAI Star Special Proficiency Mark:

- Class 7 Passed 1 Star TKK PAI
- Class 8 Passed 1st and 2nd Star TKK PAI
- Class 9 Passed 1,2 and 3 Stars TKK PAI

6. Minimum student attendance percentage is 85%

7. Have a TCB value as character development for Darul Hikam Junior High School students, at least 'Developing'

From the description of the results of character education management implemented at Darul Hikam Junior High School, in terms of management all processes, including planning, organizing, implementing and supervising, went very well. Character education management that is implemented well has an impact on the quality of graduates from Darul Hikam Junior High School students. When a graduate of Darul Hikam Junior High School is declared to have graduated from Darul Hikam Junior High School, the student will have at least:

1. Disciplined attitude because the requirement to graduate is a minimum of 85% school attendance;
2. Caring attitude because the student must complete 250 social workbook points as long as he is a Darul Hikam Junior High School student;
3. An attitude of self-confidence and never giving up because as long as you are a Darul Hikam Junior High School student, all lessons must be completed, because at Darul Hikam Junior High School a mastery learning system applies. Students will struggle to complete each lesson through remedial teaching, projects, assignments and tests until they meet the mastery learning requirements;

4. Have at least proficient Tahsin skills, meaning that a Darul Hikam Junior High School student will read the Qur'an very well;
5. Have memorized at least 3 chapters of the Qur'an;
6. Have knowledge about Islam because you have passed the PAI Proficiency Star.

Darul Hikam Junior High School students who receive character education and have a target of achieving graduation, adapt to the education pattern at Darul Hikam Junior High School, as a result they achieve several achievements and show the quality of Darul Hikam Junior High School students.

CONCLUSION

From the research data obtained by researchers after carrying out research at Darul Hikam Junior High School in Bandung, in general the researchers found that character education was implemented at Darul Hikam Junior High School and had a very big influence on the quality of graduating students from Darul Hikam Junior High School.

The implementation of character education is carried out in accordance with the school's vision which directs education towards the formation of Muslim graduates/cadres of national leaders who have strong character. With the motto "Achieving Morals", Darul Hikam Junior High School prioritizes the formation of morals. By promoting the 7 Values of Taqwa Character Buildings and adding the strengthening of the 10 Cultures of Achievement Morals.

Character education must also be planned carefully based on analysis of the achievements of previous school programs, input from parents through parent satisfaction surveys and community demands. This planning must be carried out by all school members and this planning must cover all aspects of education in the school with maximum targets for achievement.

The organization of human resources or school assets must be managed effectively and efficiently so that the implementation of character-based education can be translated into implementation that will produce maximum results. Prioritize achievement programs in accordance with school targets. With regard to character education, all resources must be involved in achieving the target.

Supervision of the implementation of character education must also be sustainable and focus on the process, because character education which will lead to a culture that will be attached to students, must be strengthened in a process, because a good process will produce good results (output).

Instruments for implementing character-based education must be comprehensive and show process achievements (daily, weekly, monthly, semester and yearly). Because character is assessed, the assessment must also look at the extent to which there are changes in attitudes and behavior in students, because the output of this process is students with character.

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